

Intricacies of Duality: Binary Intuitionistic Open Sets Explored

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ABSTRACT

The basics of topology includes the most important sets called open sets. Intuitionistic open sets exists as the basic sets for Intuitionistic Topological Space(ITS). In this article different kinds of intuitionistic open set in a special space namely binary intuitionistic topological space is introduced. Binary intuitionistic open-sets (B_1OS) namely binary intuitionistic semi- open-sets, binary intuitionistic pre- open-sets, binary intuitionistic α - open-sets are newly defined and their features existing are studied. Binary intuitionistic interior and binary intuitionistic closure of the these open sets are defined and few of its characteristics are discussed.

Keywords: BIP, BVIP, binary intuitionistic neighborhood structures and BITS.

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1 Introduction

Zadeh. L. A introduced fuzzy sets (L.A.Zadeh, 1965), which has numerous applications both theoretically and practically. Furthermore the eminence of fuzzy theory, intuitionistic fuzzy set came into existence, which is a notion by Atanassov and D.Coker (K. Atanassov, 1986)(D.Coker, 1996). Different types of open sets namely intuitionistic semi, pre and α - open sets in intuitionistic topology (IT) were introduced by authors (S.Girija and Gnanambal Ilango, 2014). The properties of these sets were studied in detail earlier. Binary topology applications in soft sets are discussed in (S.Hussain, 2020). Further binary intuitionistic open sets were introduced and their properties of neighborhoods were discussed in (L.Vidyarani and A.G.Rose Venish, 2023). As an extension of this work binary intuitionistic semi open, binary intuitionistic pre- open and binary intuitionistic α - open sets respectively in binary intuitionistic topology were introduced in this article. Description of such sets which exists naturally were studied and the behaviour of these sets in fundamental topological spaces were discussed.

2 Preliminaries

A remark illustrates theorems and fundamental definitions are conferred in this section in order to illustrate the idea introduced in this article.

Remark 2.1. For definitions of intuitionistic set and IT refer (D.Coker, 1996), intuitionistic (α -open, semi-open, pre -open and β -open regular- open) sets (S.Girija and Gnanambal Ilango, 2014), binary-intuitionistic set, topology, interior, closure, binary intuitionistic point, their properties (L.Vidharani and A.G.Rose Venish, 2023).

3 Binary intuitionistic open sets

This section brings out the definition of different forms of binary intuitionistic open- sets namely binary intuitionistic semi- open- sets (B_IOS), binary intuitionistic pre- open sets (B_IPOS) & binary intuitionistic α - open- sets ($B_I\alpha OS$) and definitions respective to their interior and closure are also defined.

Definition 3.1. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let (D, C) be a binary intuitionistic set in (T, S) then (D, C) is a binary intuitionistic semi-open set (BISOS) if $(D, C) \subseteq B_Icl(B_Iint(D, C))$. Complement of BISOS is binary intuitionistic semi closed (BISCS).

Definition 3.2. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let (C, D) be a binary intuitionistic set in (T, S) then (C, D) is a binary intuitionistic pre-open set (BIPOS) if $(C, D) \subseteq B_Iint(B_Icl(C, D))$. Complement of BIPOS is binary intuitionistic pre closed (BIPCS).

Definition 3.3. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let (C, D) be a binary intuitionistic set in (T, S) then (C, D) is said to be a binary intuitionistic α open set ($B_I\alpha OS$) if $(C, D) \subseteq B_Iint(B_Icl(B_Iint(C, D)))$. The complement of every $(B_I\alpha OS)$ is said to be binary intuitionistic α closed set ($(B_I\alpha CS)$).

Definition 3.4. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let C be a binary intuitionistic set, then the binary intuitionistic semi interior ($B_I sint$), binary intuitionistic semi closure ($B_I scl$), the binary intuitionistic pre interior ($B_I pint$), binary intuitionistic pre closure ($B_I pcl$), the binary intuitionistic α interior ($B_I\alpha int$), the binary intuitionistic α closure ($B_I\alpha cl$) of C are defined as:

1. The binary intuitionistic semi interior ($B_I sint(C)$) of C is largest binary intuitionistic semi open set $\subseteq C$.
2. The binary intuitionistic semi closure C is the smallest binary intuitionistic semi closed set containing C and it is denoted by $B_I scl(C)$.
3. The binary intuitionistic pre interior of C is largest BIPOS $\subseteq C$ and it is denoted by $B_I pint(C)$.
4. The binary intuitionistic pre closure C is the smallest binary intuitionistic pre closed set containing C and it is denoted by $B_I pcl(C)$.
5. The binary intuitionistic α interior of C is largest $B_I\alpha OS \subseteq C$ and it is denoted by $B_I\alpha int(C)$.

6. The binary intuitionistic α closure ($B_{I\alpha}cl(C)$) C is the smallest binary intuitionistic α closed set containing C .

Theorem 3.1. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and $\{E_\alpha/\alpha \in J\}$ be a family of BIOS. Then $\cup\{E_\alpha/\alpha \in J\}$ is BIOS.

Proof For each α , since E_α is a BIOS, there exists a BIOS F_α such that $F_\alpha \subset E_\alpha \subset B_{I\alpha}cl(F_\alpha)$. Therefore $\cup F_\alpha \subset \cup E_\alpha \subset \cup B_{I\alpha}cl(F_\alpha)$, since $F_\alpha \subset \cup F_\alpha$, $B_I(F_\alpha) \subset B_{I\alpha}cl(F_\alpha)$ and hence $\cup B_{I\alpha}cl(F_\alpha)$. Therefore $\cup F_\alpha \subset B_Icl(\cup F_\alpha \subset \cup E_\alpha \subset \cup B_{I\alpha}cl(F_\alpha) \subset B_Icl(\cup F_\alpha)$ which implies that $\cup E_\alpha$ is a BIOS.

4 Properties of binary intuitionistic semi open sets

Few properties of binary intuitionistic semi open sets are studied in this section.

Theorem 4.1. A subset E in a BITS (T, S, B_I) is a BISOS iff $E \subset B_Icl(B_Iint(E))$.

Proof. Necessity :Let E be BISOS. Then \exists a BIOS F , s.t $F \subset E \subset B_Icl(F)$, but $F \subset B_Iint(E)$ and thus $B_Icl(F) \subset B_Icl(B_Iint(E))$. Hence $E \subset B_Icl(F) \subset B_Icl(B_Iint(E))$.

Sufficiency : Let $E \subset B_Icl(B_Iint(E))$. We have $B_Iint(E) \subset E$. Then for $B_Iint(E) \subset E \subset B_Icl(B_I(F))$. Take $U = B_Iint(E)$, we get $U \subseteq E \subseteq B_Icl(U) \Rightarrow E$ is BISOS. \square

Remark 4.1. Intersection of 2 BISOS need not be BISOS.

Example 4.2. Suppose $T = \{a\}$ and $S = \{1, 2\}$ and let (T, S, B_I) be any binary space and $B_I = \{(\underline{T}, \underline{S}), (\phi, \phi),$

$(\langle T, \phi, \{a\} \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \phi \rangle)\}$ Here the BISOS are $\{(\underline{T}, \underline{S}), (\phi, \phi), (\langle T, \{a\}, T \rangle, \langle S, \{a\}, \{a\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle)\}$.

Intersection of $(\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1\} \rangle)$ and $(\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle)$ is $(\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1, 2\} \rangle)$ which is not a BISOS.

Theorem 4.3. Let (T, S, B_I) be any binary intuitionistic space. If E is a BIOS & B , a BISOS, then $E \cap B$ is a BIOS.

Proof. \because B is a binary intuitionistic semi open , \exists binary intuitionistic open set F such that $F \subset B \subset B_Icl(F)$ and so $E \cap F \subset E \cap B \subset E \cap B_Icl(F)$. Since $E \cap F$ is a binary intuitionistic open set, $E \cap F = B_Iint(E \cap F)$ and by theorem $E \cap B_Icl(F)$. Therefore $E \cap B \subset E \cap B_Icl(F) \subset B_Icl(E \cap F) = B_Icl(B_Iint(E \cap B))$. Hence $E \cap B$ is a binary intuitionistic semi open set. \square

Remark 4.2. If U is binary intuitionistic open in (T, S) , then U is binary intuitionistic semi open in (T, S) . Thus (T, S, B_I) be a binary intuitionistic topological space. Let B_I be set of all BIOSs in (T, S) , then (i) $B_I \subset BISOS$

(ii) For $A \in BIOS$ and $A \subset B \subset B_Icl(A)$ then $B \in BIOS$. Converse of (i) need not be true.

Example 4.4. Suppose $T = \{a\}$ and $S = \{1, 2\}$ and let (T, S, B_I) be any binary space and $B_I = \{(\underline{T}, \underline{S}), (\phi, \phi),$

$(\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \{2\} \rangle)$, the binary intuitionistic semi open sets are $\{(T, S), (\phi, \phi), (\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle)\}$.

Let $A = \langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle$ here A is BISOS but not BIOS.

Theorem 4.5. A is binary intuitionistic semi closed set iff \exists a binary intuitionistic closed set F s.t $B_{Iint}F \subseteq C \subseteq F$.

Proof. Let C be a binary intuitionistic semi open then $B_{Iint}(B_{Icl}(C)) \subseteq C$. Let $B_{Icl}(C) = B$. Then B is binary intuitionistic closed sets. Here $B_{Iint}(B) \subseteq C \subseteq B$. Thus if C is a BISOS there exists BICS F such that $B_{Iint}F \subseteq C \subseteq F$.

Conversely assume F to be BICS s.t $B_I - Int(F \subseteq C \subseteq F)$. WKT $C \subseteq F \Rightarrow B_{Icl}(C) \subseteq B_{Icl}(F)$ which implies $B_{Iint}(B_{Icl}(C)) \subseteq B_{Iint}(B_{Icl}(F)) = B_{Iint}(F)$ (Since F is binary intuitionistic closed set). $B_{Icl}(F) = F \subseteq C$ implies C is BISOS. \square

Theorem 4.6. For any BIS C in (S, T, B_I) , we have

(a) $B_{I scl}(C^c) = B_{I sint}(C)^c$

(b) $B_{I scl}(C^c) = B_{I scl}(C)^c$.

Proof. (i) $B_{I scl}(A^c) = B_{I scl}(((S, T) - A)^c) = B_{I scl}((S, T) - A)$
 $= \cup\{K/KisanBISCSin(S, T) \text{ and } (S, T) - C \subset K\}$. Therefore $(S, T) - B_{I scl}((T, S) - C)$
 $= \{(S, T) - K / (S, T) - K \text{ is an BISOS in } (S, T) \text{ and } (S, T) - K \subset C\}$
 $= \cup\{G/G \text{ is a BISOS in } (S, T) \text{ and } G \subset C\}$
 $= B_{I sint}(C)$. Therefore $B_{I scl}(C^c) = (B_{I sint}(C))^c$.

(ii) $B_{I sint}(C^c) = B_{I sint}((S, T) - C) = \cup\{G/G \text{ is a BISOS in } (S, T) \text{ and } G \subset (S, T) - C\}$, $(S, T) - B_{I sint}((S, T) - C) = \cap\{(S, T) - G / (S, T) - G / (S, T) - G \text{ is a BISCS in } (S, T) \text{ and } C \subset (S, T) - G\}$
 $= \cap\{B/B \text{ is a BISCS in } (S, T) \text{ and } C \subset B\}$. Hence $(S, T) - B_{I sint}((S, T) - C) = B_{I scl}(C)$.
Hence $(S, T) - B_{I scl}(C) = B_{I scl}(C) = B_{I sint}((S, T) - C)$. Hence $B_{I sint}(C^c) = (B_{I scl}(C))^c$. \square

Theorem 4.7. Let C be a subset of (T, S) . Then below are equal:

(a) C is an BISOS.

(b) $C \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$.

(c) $B_{Icl}(C) = B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b). Let C is a BISOS. Then \exists an BIOS G s.t $G \subset C \subset B_{Icl}(G)$. $\therefore G$ is a BIOS, $G = B_{Iint}(G)$ and so $C \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(G))$. $\therefore G \subset C$, then $C \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). $B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C)) \subset B_{Icl}(C)$.

Hence $B_{Icl}(C) \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C)))$

$= B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$. Hence $B_{Icl}(C) = B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$.

(c) \Rightarrow (a) $\therefore B_{Iint}(C) \subset C \subset B_{Icl}(C) = B_{Icl}(B_{Iint}(C))$, C is a BISOS. \square

5 Properties of binary intuitionistic pre- open sets

In this section some of the binary intuitionistic pre open sets (B_IPOS) properties are illustrated.

Theorem 5.1. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and $\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ be a family of BIPOS in (T, S, B_I) . Then $\cup\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ is a BIPOS.

Proof. Suppose $\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ be family of BIPOS in (T, S, B_I) . Then for every α , $A_\alpha \subset B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A_\alpha))$. Since $A_\alpha \subset \cup A_\alpha$, $B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A_\alpha)) \subset B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(\cup A_\alpha))$ and also $A_\alpha \subset B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(\cup A_\alpha))$. Hence $\cup A_\alpha \subset B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(\cup A_\alpha))$ which implies that $\cup A_\alpha$ is a BIPOS. \square

Remark 5.1. Intersection of two BIPOS need not be BIPOS.

Example 5.2. Suppose $T = \{a\}$ and $S = \{1, 2\}$ and let (T, S, B_I) be any binary space and $B_I = \{(\underline{T}, \underline{S}), (\phi, \phi),$

$(\langle T, \phi, \{a\} \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \phi \rangle)\}$

Here the binary intuitionistic pre open sets are $\{(\underline{T}, \underline{S}), (\phi, \phi), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \{a\}, T \rangle, \langle S, S, \{a\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, T \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \{2\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, S, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, S \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \phi \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{1\} \rangle), (\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \phi, \{2\} \rangle)\}$.

Intersection of $(\langle T, T, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle)$ and $(\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle)$ is $(\langle T, \phi, \phi \rangle, \langle S, \{1\}, \phi \rangle)$ which is not a BIPOS.

Theorem 5.3. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS. If A and B are any two BIOS in (T, S, B_I) and one of which is a BIOS, then $A \cap B$ is a BIPOS.

Proof. Let A and B be two BIPOS in (T, S, B_I) . Suppose A is a BIPOS and B is a BIOS. Then $A \subseteq B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A))$. Now $A \cap B \subset B_I - \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A) \cap B) = B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A)) \cap B_I \text{int}(B) = B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A) \cap B) \subset B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}[A \cap B])$. Hence $A \cap B$ is a BIPOS. \square

Theorem 5.4. Suppose (T, S, B_I) be a BITS. A be a BIPOS & B be a BIS s.t $B \subseteq A \subseteq B_I \text{cl}(B)$. Then B is also a BIPOS.

Proof. $A \subseteq B_I \text{cl}(B)$ implies that $B_I \text{cl}(A) \subseteq B_I \text{cl}(B)$ and so $A \subseteq B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A)) \subseteq B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(B))$ and so $B \subseteq B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(B))$. Therefore B is also a BIPOS. \square

Theorem 5.5. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and A is a BIS. Then

- (a) $B_I \text{pcl}(A^c) = B_I \text{pint}(A)$.
- (b) $B_I \text{pint}(A^c) = (B_I \text{pcl}(A))^c$.

Proof. (a) $B_I \text{pcl}(A^c) = ((T, S) - A) \cup B_I \text{cl}(B_I \text{int}((T, S) - A)) = ((T, S) - A) \cup (A - B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A))) = (B_I \text{pint}(A))^c$

(b) $B_I \text{pint}(A^c) = ((T, S) - A) \cup B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}((T, S) - A)) = ((T, S) - A) \cup (A - B_I \text{int}(B_I \text{cl}(A))) = (B_I \text{pcl}(A))^c$. \square

Theorem 5.6. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let A be a BIS. Below are equivalent:

- (a) A is a BIPCS.

- (b) $B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A)) \subseteq A$.
- (c) $B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(A^c)) \supseteq A^c$.
- (d) A^c is a BIPOS.

Proof. (a) \Rightarrow (b) If A is a BIPOS, then $(T, S) - A$ is a BIPOS and so $(T, S) - A \subset B_{Int}(B_{Icl}((T, S) - A))$. Hence $(T, S) - B_{Int}(B_{Icl}((T, S) - A)) \subset A \Rightarrow$ that $B_{Icl}(B_{Int}((T, S) - A)) \subset A$.

(b) \Rightarrow (c) WRT (b) $B_{Int}[B_{Icl}(A)] \subseteq A$ and so $(T, S) - A \subset (T, S) - B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A))) \Rightarrow B_{Icl}(B_{Int}([T, S] - A)) \supseteq A$.

(c) \Rightarrow (d) By definition A, A^c is a BIPOS.

(d) \Rightarrow (a) using definition, A is a BIPCS. □

Theorem 5.7. Let (X, Y, B_I) be a BITS and let A and B be BIS. Then the following are true.

(a) $B_{Ipcl}(\phi) = \phi$ and $B_{Ipcl}(X, Y) = (X, Y)$.

(b) A is a BIPOS iff $A = B_{Ipcl}(A)$.

(c) $B_{Ipcl}(B_{Ipcl}(A)) = B_{Ipcl}(A)$.

(d) $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow B_{Ipcl}(A) \subseteq B_{Ipcl}(B)$.

(e) $B_{Ipcl}[A \cap B] \subseteq B_{Ipcl}(A) \cap B_{Ipcl}(B)$.

(f) $B_{Ipcl}[A \cup B] = B_{Ipcl}(A) \cup B_{Ipcl}(B)$.

Proof. (a) Let A be a BIOS. Then $A = B_{Int}(A)$. Now $B_{Icl}(A) = B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(A)) \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A)))$. hence $B_{Icl}(A) \subset B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A)))$.

Again $B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A))) \subset B_{Icl}(A)$.

Thus $B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A))) = B_{Icl}(A)$.

(b) If K is BICS then $(X, Y) - K$ is BIOS and so $B_{Icl}((X, Y) - K)$ is BIRCS by (a). Hence $(X, Y) - (B_{Icl}((X, Y) - K))$ then $B_{Int}(K)$ is a BIOS.

(c) Using (b) and since $B_{Icl}(A)$ is a BICS, then $B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(A))$ is BIOS.

(d) Using (a) and since $B_{Int}(A)$ is a BIOS, then $B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(A))$ is BIOS.

Using the definitions of B_{Int} and B_{Icl} (e) and (f) may be proved. □

6 Properties of binary intuitionistic α -open sets

In this section some of the binary intuitionistic α open sets (B_IPOS) properties are illustrated.

Theorem 6.1. Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and $\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ be a family of $B_{I\alpha}OS$ in (T, S, B_I) . Then $\cup\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ is a $B_{I\alpha}OS$.

Proof. Suppose $\{A_\alpha : \alpha \in K\}$ be a family of binary intuitionistic α open set in (T, S, B_I) . Then for each A_α , $A_\alpha \subset B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(A_\alpha)))$. Since $A_\alpha \subset \cup A_\alpha$, for each α , $A_\alpha \subset B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(A_\alpha))) \subset B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(\cup A_\alpha)))$ and so $\cup A_\alpha \subset B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(B_{Int}(\cup A_\alpha)))$. □

Theorem 6.2. Suppose A be a subset of (T, S, B_I) . Then A is $B_{I\alpha}OS$ iff \exists a BIOS such that $B \subseteq A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Icl}(B))$.

Proof. Suppose that \exists a BIOS B such that $B \subseteq A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B))$. Since $A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B)) = B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B))) \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(A)))$, by the definition and by hypothesis, A is Bl α OS. On the other hand, let A be a Bl α OS. Then $A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(A)))$. Let $B_{Int}(A) = B$. Since $B_{Int}(A) \subseteq A$, we have $B \subseteq A$ and also $A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B))$. Hence \exists a BIOS such that $B \subseteq A \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B))$. \square

Theorem 6.3. *Let A be a subset of a BITS (T, S, B_I) . Then A is a Bl α OS iff $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))) \subseteq A$.*

Proof. Let A be a subset of a BITS (T, S, B_I) . So A^c is a Bl α OS. Therefore by definition, $A^c \subseteq B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(A^c))) = B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B_{Cl}(A^c))) = B_{Int}[B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))]^c = [B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A)))]^c$ which gives $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))) \subseteq A$. By the definitions and by hypothesis converse part is true. \square

Theorem 6.4. *Let A be a subset of a BITS (T, S, B_I) . Then A is Bl α OS iff \exists BICS B s.t $B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B)) \subseteq A \subseteq B$.*

Proof. Let A be a Bl α OS. Then $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))) \subseteq A$. Let $B_{Cl}(A) = B$. Then B is BICS. Since $A \subseteq B_{Cl}(A)$, $A \subseteq B$ and $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))) \subseteq A \Rightarrow B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B)) \subseteq A$. Thus there exists BICS B s.t $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B)) \subseteq A \subseteq B$. Conversely assume that there exists BICS B s.t $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B)) \subseteq A \subseteq B$.

Since B is BICS, then $B_{Cl}(B) = B$. By hypothesis, $B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B)) \subseteq A \Rightarrow B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B))) \subseteq A$.

Since $A \subseteq B \Rightarrow B_{Cl}(A) \subseteq B_{Cl}(B)$

$\Rightarrow B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(A))) \subseteq B_{Cl}(B_{Int}(B_{Cl}(B))) \subseteq A \Rightarrow A$ Bl α OS. \square

Theorem 6.5. *Let (T, S, B_I) be a BITS and let D and C be BITS in (T, S) . Then*

(a) *D is a Bl α OS in (T, S, B_I) iff $D = B_I\alpha cl(D)$.*

(b) *D is a Bl α CS in (T, S, B_I) iff $D = B_I\alpha int(D)$.*

(c) *$B_I\alpha cl(\phi) = \phi$ and $B_I\alpha cl((T, S)) = (T, S)$.*

(d) *$B_I\alpha int(\phi) = \phi$ and $B_I\alpha int((T, S)) = (T, S)$.*

(e) *$B_I\alpha int(B_I\alpha int(D)) = B_I\alpha int(D^c)$.*

(f) *$(B_I\alpha cl(D))^c = B_I\alpha int(D^c)$.*

(g) *$B_I\alpha int(D)^c = B_I\alpha cl(D)^c$.*

(h) *$D \subseteq C \Rightarrow B_I\alpha int(D) \subseteq B_I\alpha int(C)$.*

(i) *$D \subseteq C \Rightarrow B_I\alpha cl(D) \subseteq B_I\alpha cl(C)$.*

(j) *$B_I\alpha cl(D \cup C) = B_I\alpha cl(D) \cup B_I\alpha cl(C)$.*

(k) *$B_I\alpha int(D \cap C) = B_I\alpha int(D) \cap B_I\alpha int(C)$.*

(l) *$B_I\alpha cl(D \cap C) = B_I\alpha cl(D) \cap B_I\alpha cl(C)$.*

(m) *$B_I\alpha int(D \cup C) = B_I\alpha int(D) \cup B_I\alpha int(C)$.*

Proof. By the definitions of Bl α OS, closure and interior definitions and by using the usual operators the theorem is proved. \square

Conclusion

Further applications of the binary intuitionistic open sets, introduced in this article on fuzzy space, fine space, which would bring more applications in the areas of digital lines, computer networking, data analysis, decision making problems, medicine etc., and also this article serves as the base for future applications of *BIOS* in binary intuitionistic fine topology and binary intuitionistic fuzzy topology.

Reference

- K. ATANASSO: *Intuitionistic fuzzy sets*, Fuzzy Sets and System, **20(1)** (1986), 87-96.
- D.COKEER: *A note on intuitionistic sets and intuitionistic points*, Turkish Journal of Mathematics, **20(3)** (1996), 343-351.
- D. COKEER: *An introduction to Intuitionistic fuzzy topological spaces*, Fuzzy Sets and System, **88(2000)**, 81-89.
- S.GIRIJA AND GNANAMBAL ILANGO : *Some more results on intuitionistic semi open sets*, International Journal of Engineering Research and Applications, **4(11)** (2014), 70 - 74.
- N.LEVINE : *Semi open sets and semi-continuity in topological spaces*, Americal Mathematical Monthly, **70** (1963), 36 - 41.
- S.NITHYANANTHA JOTHI AND P.THANGAVELU : *Topology between two sets*, Journal of Mathematical Sciences and computer applications, **1(3)** (2011), 95 - 107.
- S. PREMA, D. JAYANTHI : *Intuitionistic Fuzzy Almost γ Generalized Closed Mappings*, International Journal of Mathematics and Statistics, **22(2)** (2022), 17-30.
- HOSSEIN RASHMANLOU, MOSTAFA NOURI JOUYBARI, S. FIROUZIAN, P.K. KISHORE KUMAR : *A Study on Irregular Intuitionistic Fuzzy Graphs*, International Journal of Mathematics and Computation, **29(2)** (2018), 17 - 28.
- S.HUSSAIN: *An Application Of Binary Soft Mappings To The Problem In Medical Expert Systems*, Journal of applied mathematics and informatics, **38(5-6)** (2020), 533 - 545.
- G.SASIKALA AND M. NAVANEETHA KRISHNAN : *Study on intuitionistic semi open sets*, IOSR Journal of Mathematics, **12(6)** (2016), 79 - 84.
- G.SASIKALA AND M. NAVANEETHA KRISHNAN : *On intuitionistic pre open sets*, International Journal of Pure and applied Mathematics, **116(24)** (2017), 281 - 292.
- G.SASIKALA AND M. NAVANEETHA KRISHNAN : *Study on intuitionistic α open sets and α closed sets*, International Journal of Mathematical Archive, **8(1)** (2017), 26 - 30.
- A.G.ROSE VENISH, L.VIDYARANI AND M. VIGNESHWARAN: *On Binary Neutrosophic Crisp Points And Binary Neutrosophic Neighborhoods*, Journal of Neutrosophic and Fuzzy Systems, 5(1), 15-22 (2023).
- L.VIDYARANI AND A.G.ROSE VENISH: *On binary intuitionistic points and intuitionistic neighborhood structures*, AIP Conference Proceedings, **2699(1)**, 020014 (2023).
- L.A.ZADEH: *Fuzzy sets*, Information and Control, **8** (1965), 338-353.